

Section of the conference: Social Sciences | Sekcja konferencji: Nauki społeczne

How to cite: Pitsou, C., & Zotou, A. (2025). Embedding Children's Rights Education in Early Childhood: Fostering a Democratic Classroom Atmosphere?. *International Conference on Next-Generation Innovations and Sustainability 2025*. Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114164>

Embedding Children's Rights Education in Early Childhood: Fostering a Democratic Classroom Atmosphere?

Charikleia Pitsou¹, Aikaterini Zotou²

¹ PhD, Special Teaching Staff, Department of Educational Sciences and Social Work, University of Patras, Greece, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0369-316X>

² Med, Pre-primary Educator, Patras, Greece, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-2292-9475>

Accepted: March 14, 2025 | **Published:** March 31, 2025 | **Language:** English

Abstract: The present study aimed to examine the educational practices that early childhood educators in Greece choose to incorporate into Child Rights Education and whether these practices contribute to fostering a democratic classroom atmosphere. Twelve kindergarten teachers in western Greece participated in this qualitative research through interviews. The results of the study showed that survey participants adopt a variety of practices aligned with Children's Rights Education, contributing to the development of a democratic classroom atmosphere. However, further research is needed on the questioning topic to examine the long-term impact of such rights-based educational practices on children's development and their civic engagement.

Keywords: child rights, democratic school climate, educational practices, kindergarten teachers, interviews.

Introduction

Children's Rights (CR) recognition and promotion through the educational process are considered essential and should ideally begin at an early stage, starting from preschool education (Quennerstedt, 2016). At this age, children are at a peak stage of their overall development, making early intervention crucial (Kükürtcü & Erkan, 2022). UNICEF's Private Fundraising and Partnership Division (UNICEF PFP, 2014) officially recognized Children's Rights Education (CRE) as a core objective in 2014. This aimed to ensure that children gain an understanding of their rights through educational programs that highlight their role as rights holders and relate learning to their everyday experiences. According to UNICEF's handbook (ibid), CRE should focus on three key aspects: (a) enhancing children's awareness and understanding of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (United Nations General Assembly, 1989), (b) implementing practices that uphold and encourage these rights, and (c) equipping children to actively advocate for children's rights and hold duty bearers accountable.

To achieve the aforementioned goals, educators play a crucial role, as they ought to serve as role models by respecting and promoting CR across all subject areas of the curriculum (Covell et al., 2010) both inside and outside the classroom. Specifically, according to Gollob et al. (2011), there are three principles that teachers should follow to effectively implement CRE. The first principle is *non-indoctrination*, which means that teachers should not steer students toward adopting a particular viewpoint. Instead, they should encourage independent thinking by providing stimuli and facilitating discussions on various topics, allowing students to form their own opinions. The second principle is *controversial discussion*, teachers create an open and welcoming environment for differing perspectives among students, using these moments as opportunities for constructive dialogue. The third principle is *student empowerment*, which involves enabling students to advocate for their interests. This means allowing them to select topics of interest during lesson planning, fostering active participation and engagement in the learning process. In accordance with Gollob & Krapf (2008), CRE as well as human rights education, should be based on three pedagogical approaches. The first is learning "about" rights, which focuses on acquiring knowledge about rights and democracy. The second is learning "through" rights, meaning that children's rights education should be integrated into all subjects within the curriculum and taught in ways that align with children's rights principles. The third approach is learning "for" rights and democracy, which emphasizes the connection between students' school experiences and issues that concern them both in the present and in their future lives. If these pedagogical approaches are adopted in the implementation of CRE, they can contribute to the development of a democratic classroom atmosphere.

A democratic classroom atmosphere is characterized by several key elements that create an inclusive and participatory learning environment. These include fostering students' active participation, ensuring equal access and opportunities, and promoting freedom of expression and speech. Additionally, it involves embracing diversity, recognizing individual contributions, and positioning the teacher as a role model and exemplar. In such an environment, teachers develop close and familiar relationships with students, maintaining an open and respectful attitude toward diversity.

Furthermore, shared decision-making, student involvement in evaluation, and a focus on both personal and academic development play a crucial role in strengthening democratic values within the classroom (Berliana & Habiby, 2024; Korth, 2024). Based on the above, the purpose of this study is to investigate which educational practices the participating early childhood educators choose to integrate into the CRE and whether these practices promote the development of a democratic school atmosphere. This research is crucial because there is not many studies that detail the process of establishing a democratic classroom atmosphere through CRE in Greece.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The purpose of the present study seeks to examine: a) the educational practices that early childhood educators choose to incorporate into CRE and b) if these practices contribute to fostering a democratic learning atmosphere. The paper addressed the following two research questions:

1st: What educational practices do early childhood educators choose to implement in relation to CRE?

2nd: Do these educational practices contribute to shaping a democratic classroom atmosphere?

In order to respond to these research questions, semi-structured interviews with twelve kindergarten teachers in western Greece were undertaken. All the survey participants worked in kindergarten schools. The research conducted was qualitative. A pilot interview was conducted. The selection of the participants followed the deliberate and snowballing sampling methods. The protocol of the current semi-structured interview emerged especially from the study of literature and a number of related studies. The interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed verbatim. The analysis of the research data was performed with thematic analysis (Creswell, 2012). Recurring patterns in the survey participants' narratives were identified and organized into themes. Reliability and validity standards as well as ethical ones were adhered to throughout the research process.

Research Results

Two themes are generated through qualitative data analysis. The first theme includes the findings pertain to the educational practices selected by early childhood educators for the implementation of CRE and the second one includes the practices which contribute to cultivating a democratic school atmosphere. Specifically, the participating educators reported adopting a range of practices aimed at embedding CR within their teaching practice. These include the collaborative establishment of classroom rules with children (Int.10), resulting in the formulation and continuous development of a class contract to ensure a well-functioning school environment based on mutual respect and the safeguarding of all rights (Int.1, Int.9). Additionally, practices such as encouraging children's active participation in decision-making—often through voting procedures concerning the organization of the daily schedule (Int.1, Int.2, Int.6)—and fostering children's agency by assigning them responsibilities and promoting initiative-taking (Int.1, Int.9, Int.12) are highlighted. Moreover, educators report utilizing classroom assistants who undertake specific roles (Int.5, Int.6) and promoting conflict resolution among children without teacher intervention, where feasible, through structured dialogue (Int.2, Int.9). Other noteworthy strategies include the establishment of a "calm corner" (Int.6), supporting emotional recognition and self-regulation, the implementation of class

councils (Int.2) for collective reflection and problem-solving, and fostering partnerships with parents, experts, and the broader community within the framework of related projects (Int.6, Int.10).

According to the participants, these practices actively contribute to shaping a democratic classroom atmosphere characterized by equality, diverse acceptance, and psychological safety. The creation of such a climate enables children to perceive themselves as valued members of a school space where their individuality, voices, emotions, and needs are acknowledged and respected. Within this context, children are encouraged to engage freely with peers and adults, express their opinions, participate in discussions, make choices regarding their activities, and play an active role in shaping initiatives that concern them. This framework facilitates both the enjoyment of their rights and the concurrent understanding and fulfillment of their responsibilities.

To further illustrate the above findings, selected interview excerpts are presented below:

Int.1: "...We try to help one another and to collaborate... We always ask if someone needs help without pressuring or forcing them... we encourage children to take initiative and assume responsibilities; we try, as much as possible, to foster their independence, to empower them to act on their own and resolve certain situations independently..."

Int.12: "I try to encourage each child, to give them as many incentives as possible so they can take initiative... to feel emotionally empowered."

Int.9: "... Do they have conflicts? From the very beginning, the children learn that when there is a conflict, say over a toy, they should discuss why they are arguing. I have a special spot, a nice little bench, where they go to resolve their disagreements. I've told them: 'You'll sit on the bench for a while and discuss what the problem is, and when you find a solution, you can come and let me know. Then you can go back to playing with the toy.' There is a rule here, something we have already agreed upon in our classroom contract."

Int.2: "In the activities we organize in class, the children also have the right to choose or share their opinion about what we could do, or what they would like us to do in class. They participate in organizing the program, in a way... For example, I may have planned an activity, and they might want to change it. Maybe it doesn't include music, and they want to add a song. So, we adjust the activity according to their choices."

Int.8: "I generally teach children that... everyone is free, they have the right to freedom, they have the right to use their free time to play as they wish, to draw whatever they like... but my right ends where the right of another begins... my freedom ends where someone else's freedom begins. So, there is respect for everyone... we have rights in school, we have the autonomy to do what we want, but we should not abuse it—we don't do to others what we wouldn't want done to us."

Int.11: "Well, the classroom, the environment, is gradually organized, and certain rules and routines are established. Through them, children learn structure, they learn to navigate their classroom space, they learn about boundaries—their own and those of others. This is essential for smooth functioning and the participation of all, and I believe this environment promotes respect for others' rights as well."

Int.5: "...I promote rights by shaping the classroom setting and assigning classroom helpers who are given specific responsibilities on a weekly basis..."

Int.6: "What matters most to me is individual freedom and the right to choose... the recognition of emotions... I have a corner with cushions—it's the calm corner... respect and acceptance are extremely important in this classroom."

Int.2: "What we do is hold a class council. When something happens in class, the whole group gathers and we discuss what bothered us, what the concern was, and we try to find solutions. Everyone shares their opinion, what happened beforehand that led to this situation, and they suggest possible solutions..."

The above narratives demonstrate how survey participants' educational practices for CRE contribute to the establishment of a democratic classroom atmosphere.

Conclusions

This study examined through qualitative method the educational practices that early childhood educators choose to implement in relation to CRE and whether they contribute to shaping a democratic school climate. Specifically, this research highlights that early childhood educators adopt a variety of practices aligned with CRE contributing to the development of a democratic school climate. The participants mainly employ interactive and experiential teaching methods, appropriate for the developmental stage of young children (Gollob & Krapf, 2008; Tibbitts, 2002; UNICEF, 2021), while fostering student agency and participation through practices such as co-creating rules, encouraging free expression, and involving children in decision-making processes (Etchebehere & De León, 2020; Gollob et al., 2011). Furthermore, collaboration with families and the community emerges as a key factor in disseminating a rights-based culture beyond the school context (Piscitelli & McArdle, 1999).

The findings are consistent with recent studies confirming the effectiveness of creative, experiential, and participatory practices in enhancing children's knowledge of their rights and sensitivity to them (Park et al., 2022; Pitsou & Theocharidi, 2024). At the same time, emphasis is placed on the creation of a safe and inclusive environment that strengthens a democratic atmosphere (Gollob & Krapf, 2009; Tellgren, 2019; Dunhill, 2018). Last but not least, the results of this study should be treated with caution as there are some limitations. It is a small-scale research in which only women took place from a specific region in Greece, and they were invited to answer self-report questions. Therefore, further research including observation is needed to investigate the effects of rights-based practices on children's civic engagement and social-emotional development as well as the challenges and impediments that arise from the implementation of CRE for kindergarten teachers. Additionally, examining the role of families and communities in supporting CRE, as well as the impact of professional training for kindergarten teachers, could further strengthen the depth and value of such a study.

References

Berliana, R. P., & Habiby, W. N. (2024). Teacher Perceptions and Implementation of a Democratic Classroom Atmosphere in Elementary Schools. *Jurnal Cakrawala Pendas*, 10(2), 318-335. <https://doi.org/10.31949/jcp.v10i2.8915>

- Covell, K., Howe, R. B., & McNeil, J. K. (2010). Implementing children's human rights education in schools. *Improving Schools*, 13(2), 117-132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480210378942>
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). MA: Pearson.
- Dunhill, A. (2018). Does teaching children about human rights, encourage them to practice, protect and promote the rights of others? *Education 3-13*, 46(1), 16-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2016.1165717>
- Etchebehere, G., & De León, D. (2020). Children's rights in the field of early education. *Early Years*, 40 (4-5), 415-428. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2020.1825340>
- Gollob, R., & Krapf, P. (Ed.). (2008). *Living in democracy. EDC/HRE lesson plans for lower secondary level*. Council of Europe Publishing. Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016802f7304>
- Gollob, R., & Krapf, P. (Ed.). (2009). *Teaching democracy. A collection of models for democratic citizenship and human rights education*. Council of Europe Publishing. Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016802f7306>
- Gollob, R., Krapf, P., & Weidinger, W. (Ed.). (2011). *Educating for Democracy. Background materials on democratic citizenship and human rights education for teachers*. Council of Europe Publishing. Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016802f727b>
- Korth, C. E. (2024). Democratic Schooling Practices. *Advances in Educational Marketing, Administration, and Leadership Book Series*, 337-382. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-0867-8.ch011>
- Kükürtcü, S. K., & Erkan, N. S. (2022). The Effects of Children's Rights and Democracy Education on Children's Democratic Behaviors. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 18(1), 174-193. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2022.426.10>
- Park, E., Park, S., & Jang, M. (2022). The effectiveness of a child rights education program in Bangladesh. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 121, 105828. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105828>
- Piscitelli, B., & McArdle, F. (1999). Children have rights: Lessons for teachers and the wider world. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 31, (1), 60-66.
- Pitsou, C., & Theocharidi, A. (2024). Integrating democratic principles in early childhood education through an art program for gender equality. *European Journal of Alternative Education Studies*, 9(2): 244-57. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejae.v9i2.5725>

- Tellgren, B. (2019). Teaching about and through children's human rights in preschool. In A. Quennerstedt (Ed.), *Teaching children's human rights in early childhood education and school. Educational aims, content and processes*, (pp. 34-55). Örebro University.
- Tibbitts, F. (2002). Understanding what we do: Emerging models for human rights education. *International review of education*, 48(3), 159-171. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020338300881>
- UNICEF (2021). *Child Rights Education with Children aged 0-6 years. Discussion paper*. <https://www.unicef.ie/app/uploads/2021/11/UNICEF-Child-Rights-Education-with-children-aged-0-6-years.pdf>
- UNICEF Private Fundraising and Partnerships Division (UNICEF PFP). (2014). *Child Rights Education Toolkit*. UNICEF PFP. <https://www.unicef.org/media/63081/file/UNICEF-Child-Rights-Education-Toolkit.pdf>
- United Nations. *Convention on the Rights of the Child*. 20 November 1989. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-child>
- Quennerstedt, A. (2016). Young children's enactments of human rights in early childhood education, *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 24(1), 5-18. DOI: 10.1080/09669760.2015.1096238